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Research Article

**ANALYSIS OF PHYSIOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE LIVER
AFTER USING PARACETAMOL EXCESSIVELY AMONG
LOCAL POPULATION OF PAKISTAN****Dr Afzal Hussain¹, Dr Ayesha Shaheen², Dr Saira Ibrahim³**¹District Head Quarter Hospital Hafizabad, ²Jinnah Hospital Lahore, ³Wazirabad Institute of Cardiology, Gujranwala.

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Abstract:

Introduction: The liver plays a part in many important functions in the body including metabolism, detoxification, and bile secretion. Additionally, it provides protection from exposure to foreign substances by detoxifying and eliminating them.

Aims of the study: The basic aim of the study is to analyze the physiological changes in the liver after using paracetamol excessively among local population of Pakistan.

Material and methods: This cross sectional study was conducted in District Head Quarter Hospital Hafizabad during January 2018 till May 2018. This study was done with the permission of ethical research committee of the department. The data was collected from 50 patients who were using the paracetamol excessively. 5ml blood was taken for further analysis. Blood was centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 10 minutes and serum was separated. Serum liver enzymes (AST, ALT and ALP) and serum Total protein level were estimated by using Human Diagnostic enzymatic kits.

Results: There was a significant increase in collagen fiber accumulation in the second and third week sections and a non-significant increase in the first week sections of the high-dose paracetamol group compared with the control group. In the control group, sections showed a normal histological pattern with seminiferous tubules and a narrow interstitium in between them. Liver histology shows that liver cell lines were destroyed mainly due to the excessive use of paracetamol.

Conclusion: It is concluded that paracetamol is harmful to the liver when consumed in large repeated doses. Thus, it should be used with caution, especially when a large and prolonged dose is indicated.

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INTRODUCTION:

The liver plays a part in many important functions in the body including metabolism, detoxification, and bile secretion. Additionally, it provides protection from exposure to foreign substances by detoxifying and eliminating them. A healthy liver is very important to overall health because it also handles the metabolism and excretion of drugs from the body [1]. Excessive exposure of the liver to environmental toxins, alcohol, drug overdose, and chemotherapeutic agents such as carbon tetrachloride (Paracetamol) and thioacetamide can damage the liver and cause alcoholic liver disease, followed by hepatitis and cirrhosis [2]. The biological activity of a chemical may be modified through prior or simultaneous exposure of a test organism to another chemical agent and such interactions might result in a potentiation, summation, or reduction of the ultimate effect of the chemical [3]. Pesticides are occasionally used indiscriminately in large amounts causing environmental pollution and therefore, area cause of concern. Organophosphorus insecticides (OPIs) are a major component of many pesticides with wide spread use in both agricultural and domestic situations [4]. However, approximately 85%-90% of applied agricultural pesticides never reach target organisms, but disperse through the air, soil, and water. Diazinon (DIA) with a broad range of insecticidal activity and widely used throughout the world with applications in agriculture and horticulture [5].

Paracetamol (known as acetaminophen in the United States) is a synthetic, nonopioid, centrally acting analgesic and antipyretic agent. Its effectiveness as an antipyretic agent has been attributed to its effect on the hypothalamic heat-regulating center [6]. Paracetamol is used in many forms either alone or in combination with other drugs (usually opiates) for analgesia and in other mixtures such as cold 'cures' for its analgesic and antipyretic properties.

The resulting oxidative stress in the cell may ultimately lead to cell death. NAPQI also binds to cell macromolecules, which can cause cell death. Chronic ethanol intake, enzyme-inducing drugs, and malnutrition are thought to increase susceptibility to paracetamol toxicity due to depletion of

intracellular GSH and greater accumulation of toxic metabolites [8].

Aims of the study

The basic aim of the study is to analyze the physiological changes in the liver after using paracetamol excessively among local population of Pakistan.

Material and methods:

This cross sectional study was conducted in District Head Quarter Hospital Hafizabad during January 2018 till May 2018. This study was done with the permission of ethical research committee of the department. The data was collected from 50 patients who were using the paracetamol excessively. The following items were recorded and analyzed for the patients: demographics (age, gender), medical past history with a special attention to chronic ethanol abuse and pre-existing signs of liver steatosis (alcoholic or non-alcoholic), outcome expressed as death or survival, the presence of organ dysfunction (encephalopathy or coma, infections, acute kidney injury with the need for extrarenal epuration, the need for mechanical ventilation, for vasopressors). 5ml blood was taken for further analysis. Blood was centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 10 minutes and serum was separated. Serum liver enzymes (AST, ALT and ALP) and serum Total protein level were estimated by using Human Diagnostic enzymatic kits.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed with commercial computer software (SPSS version 15; SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS:

There was a significant increase in collagen fiber accumulation in the second and third week sections and a non-significant increase in the first week sections of the high-dose paracetamol group compared with the control group. In the control group, sections showed a normal histological pattern with seminiferous tubules and a narrow interstitium in between them. Liver histology shows that liver cell lines were destroyed mainly due to the excessive use of paracetamol.

S.O.V	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	F	Sig.
Between Groups	12385.081	04	3096.270	23.794	.000
Within Groups	2602.510	20	130.125		
Total	14987.591	24			

Table 01: Analysis of LFTs, SD, and P-value in group II and group III compared with the control group

Comparison analysis of control and affected groups

DISCUSSION:

The use of the paracetamol treatment nomogram is restricted to patients with a known time of ingestion. It cannot be used after the following scenarios: staggered ingestions, delayed presentations (more than 24 h post-overdose), unknown time of ingestion, and repeated supratherapeutic ingestion. In most countries, the threshold for treatment is determined by a line starting at 150 mg/L at 4 h post-ingestion [6]. From a large efficacy trial of oral NAC, a small risk (1%) of hepatotoxicity was determined for patients below this threshold Paracetamol is an effective, mild analgesic, antipyretic agent and is probably the most widely used of all drugs in the world [7]. In many countries, it is fashionable to misuse over-the-counter analgesics for self-poisoning. As a result, paracetamol has become a victim of its own success. Paracetamol was administered orally in mice at two therapeutic doses: low (40 mg/kg/day) and high (80 mg/kg/day) [8]. In the present study, the doses were calculated according to Paget's formula. Damage to the structural integrity of liver is reflected by an increase in the level of serum transaminase because these are cytoplasmic in location and are released into circulation after cellular

damage. It is generally accepted that the toxicity of carbon tetrachloride depends on the cleavage of the carbon-chlorine bond to generate a trichloromethyl free radical, and this free radical reacts rapidly with oxygen to form a trichloro methyl peroxy radical, which may contribute to the hepatotoxicity and subsequent increase in hepatic enzymes [9].

An increased in liver enzymes (AST,ALT)level was investigated and decrease in total protein level in those rats which received only Paracetamol [10].This shows that Paracetamol causes hepato toxicity resulting in the increase of AST,ALT and ALP levels. The increased AST, ALT and ALP level shows an increase in cellular metabolism [11].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that paracetamol is harmful to the liver when consumed in large repeated doses. Thus, it should be used with caution, especially when a large and prolonged dose is indicated.

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